

Prophet Muhammad (s.a.w) as the best man on earth

Wafaa Talha

Phd in Islamic Sciences Candidate

International Open University

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Abstract: This research topic was selected because Prophet Muhammad is the best man on earth and needs to be discussed and the world should be taught about him and educated about him that how his example should be followed. In this research most of the aspects of his life have been highlighted and examples given so that the reader can understand how he was truly divinely inspired. Some of the questions that were answered through this research were what his instructions about neighbours to his followers was, why did he marry more than one woman, how was his behaviour towards children.

Keywords: Prophet Muhammad, Best Man.

1. INTRODUCTION

A religious, social and political leader, Muhammad bin Abdullah bin Abdul Mutalib, the Prophet of Allah, in the year of the Elephant. According to Islamic creed he was divinely inspired Prophet (salutations be upon him), the religious book of Muslims: Quran was revealed to him. The previous monotheistic religions of Adam, Ibrahim, Moses, Jesus and other prophets were affirmed by him, He is khatam al Nabiyeen, the seal of the Prophets. Arabia was organized into a single Muslim society by him, he was the leader and to date the Muslims around the world follow him. And obedience to his command is considered like the obedience to Allah.

Abdul Mutalib, his grand father named him Muhammad, and Allah has called him by this name four times in the Quran, He has also been called Prophet, Messenger, Servant of God, announcer, witness, bearer of good tidings, warner and Mudhakir. Noor and Siraj munir.

Prophet had a round, attractive and fair face, his face would shine brightly when he was pleased but would turn crimson when he was upset, the smell of his sweat was better than that of musk and his sweat on his face glistened like pearls. His eyes were wide, the pupils were black while white was mixed with crimson, his eye lashes were long and thick, eyebrows were thin and arched, cheeks soft, forehead wide, he had a wide forehead, and his cheeks were soft, he had a wide mouth and he had space between each of his teeth and they were bright and they sparkled when he spoke, and the bridge of his nose was high and shiny. He had a thick black and full beard that covered most of his chest, on his ear lobes and chin, grey hair showed.

The Prophet (salutations be upon him) had a large head on a long neck. His hair was slightly curly, and he wore it parted in the middle. Sometimes he kept his hair so long it touched both his shoulders, while at other times it fell just above his earlobes. He had a few grey hairs on his head and beard together.

The Prophet of Allah peace and blessings of Allah be upon him had large elbows, shoulders, knees and wrists, He had wide palms and feet. Heavy and hairy arms, light heels and calves. His shoulders and chest were broad and hairless chest. He was neither thin nor fat. He was of medium build. Several of the Prophet's Companions have mentioned a fragrance, sweeter than any perfume, emanating from the Prophet's body. Anas says: "I never smelt any musk or any other such

perfume that was as sweet as the fragrance of the Prophet (salutations be upon him" Jabir says: "The Prophet's fragrance lingered after he left, and we could tell which path he had taken by sniffing the air." If the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him happened to shake hands with anyone, the fragrance would remain with that person for the whole day. When he spread his hand over a child's head, others would discern his fragrance on the child. Umm Sulaym used to collect some of the Prophet's sweat in a small bottle and would mix it with perfume. The Prophet (salutations be upon him) was swift-footed and had a firm step. He would turn swiftly and gracefully. The Prophet (Salutations be upon him) never seemed to tire when he walked, and nobody could keep pace with him. Abu Hurayrah says, "I have never seen anyone who walked as quickly as the Prophet. It looked as if the earth rolled itself up for him when he walked. We would tire ourselves out walking with him, while he would move on with ease."¹

2. MAIN ARTICLE

He was a perfect human being as mentioned in the book of Allah, followed by billions of Muslims in current times and in the past since his advent. Currently there are about 1.9 billion Muslims in the world.

The Quran says, "Indeed, you are on the best of characters." about Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him.

God has sent me to perfect good manners and to do good deeds." (Bukhari)

How is it proven that Prophet Muhammad is the best Man on earth, any aspect of his life that we study, we find him equipped with qualities that are tantamount to goodness.

He was a son to parents who had died, he was an orphan. He lost his father before his birth when his mother was still pregnant with him, and he lost his mother when he was only six years old.

Abdullah bin Abdul Mutalib, the son of Quraysh tribal leader Abd al-Muttalib ibn Hashim, died a few months before Muhammad's birth the father of Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) went to Syria with one of the trade Caravans, but during his travel he fell ill, on his return journey, he stayed in Madinah to get better, Abdul mutalib his father sent the brother Haarith to find out about him but Abdullah had died before his return, and was buried in darul nabgha. At the time of death he was 25 years old. Thus, the Prophet never saw his father alive.

When the Prophet was six years old, his mother travelled with him to Madinah so that he could meet his maternal family, on this journey there were two camels, umm Aiman was with them, Amna stayed there for one month at Dar ul Nabgha where Abdullah was buried. Some seerah historians have written that Amna probably went to Syria so that they could visit the grave of Abdullah.

Both his parents died in Madinah, and he also migrated to Madinah, denoting that in Islamic history the city of Madinah has a special place. The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah) said, "O Allah! Bestow on Madinah twice the blessings You bestowed on Mecca."

He was a father, with four daughters, Umm Kulthoom, Ruqayah, Zainab and Fatimah and boys, he was ridiculed by his opponents because his son died at a young age and his hierarchy had stopped growing. The names of his three sons were Tahir, Tayyab and Abdullah. It is also narrated according to some traditions that he had one son Abdullah and Tahir and Tayyab were his names. At the death of his sons he said, that the heart is full of sorrow but the tongue will only say what pleases Allah. The dying child was placed on the Prophet's lap as life was almost departing from him. The Prophet's eyes were tearful. Saad ibn Ubadah said to him: 'What is this, Messenger of God?' He replied: 'This is compassion which God places in the hearts of those He chooses from among His servants.

It shows how he lost children but didn't complain to God, this is unlike average humans who would lament at the loss of a child. ²

¹ <https://thethinkingmuslim.com/2021/02/19/the-prophet-muhammads-pbuh-physical-features-and-character>

² <https://www.arabnews.com/node/263588#:~:text=The%20dying%20child%20was%20placed,chooses%20from%20amon%20His%20servants.>

He was an exemplary husband, husband who at one point to 11 and then finally to 9 wives by the command of Allah, not out of lust but by the command of Allah, yet he was fair with all of them, however the Muslims are only allowed to marry four wives at a time but that too if they can be fair with them, he married all these women so that Muslims learn that it is permissible to marry such women. His first marriage was with Khadijah, she was married twice before Prophet Muhammad, her first and second husband died, and she was widowed both times. When the revelation came down she was the first one to believe in him, he said, something strange had happened but she was the one who reassured him that he is a Al ameen and nothing bad will happen to him,

Among his other marriages was his marriage to Ayesha who was the daughter of Abu Bakr and Zainab his cousin, Ayesha came in his dream as a bride and the dreams of Prophets are true and his marriage with Zainab was preformed in the heavens. Similarly, his other marriages were on the basis of wisdom to show that a widowed, a divorced, an older lady, a cousin, a Jew who accepts Islam, a woman who has just attained puberty, a slave acquired etc could be married.

When asked about the behaviour of the Holy Prophet (Salutations be upon him), 'A'ishah (may Allah be pleased with her) is reported to have replied: "He excelled all men in gentle speech, smiling countenance and cheerful temperament." ³

Tirmidhi has recorded that 'A'ishah (may Allah be pleased be with her) was asked what the Holy Prophet (Salutations be upon him) did when he was in the house. She responded: "He was a man like other men; he would look after his clothes himself, he would milk the goat, he attended to his personal needs himself. In another report, in response to a similar question by Aswad bin Yazeed, she said: "He helped the members of his family in whatever they were doing and when he heard the Adhan [Call] for Prayers he proceeded to the Mosque." The Holy Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah upon him) introduced a totally new form of decorum towards women. In general, he would observe no formality or formal protocol when meeting people. He used to say: "I am not of those who adopt unnecessary formality." He would sit on the floor next to 'A'ishah (may Allah be pleased with her) and drink from the same part of the bowl that she had drunk from. When they ate, he would sometimes suck the piece of bone she had sucked, as a demonstration of his affection. ⁴

He was a leader, leader to a new emerging nation, brave, decisive and fearless. He showed this at several occasions, at the time of Hudaibiya when the Quresh wouldn't let them pass, he made a pact with them and showed his companions who were reluctant by taking the first step himself towards implementing what he had commanded. Again, he showed his leadership when he appointed Abu Bakr as the leader of the prayer when he fell ill closer to his death.

Prophet Muhammad saw in a dream that he was circumambulating the kabaa and as the dreams of the prophets are true, he made arrangements to go for this pilgrimage and took with him 1500 companions and invited the beduions but the beduions refused to go with him, they had sacrificial animals and were dressed as pilgrims but when they were close to Makkah the Quresh refused them to enter, and a cavalry of 200 stopped them, Prophet Muhammad, made a pact with them instead of opting to fight, he pitched his tents at hudaibybiya and the treaty was called the treat of hudaibybiyyah, the Quresh said, "Even if he has come not wanting to fight, by God, he shall never enter [the sanctuary] by force against our will, nor shall the bedouin ever [have cause to] say that about us". After negotiations, the parties agreed to resolve the matter peacefully and a treaty was drawn up. The main points stated:

- There will be a truce between both parties for ten years
- Whoever flees to Muhammad from the Quraysh without the permission of his guardian will be sent back to the Quraysh, but whoever comes to the Quraysh from the Muslims will not be sent back
- Whoever wishes to enter into a covenant with Muhammad will be allowed to do so, and whoever wishes to enter into a covenant with the Quraysh will be allowed to do so
- The Muslims will return to Medina without performing the pilgrimage but will be allowed the following year and would stay in Mecca for three days during which time the Quraysh will vacate the city. The Muslims will carry no weapons except sheathed swords.

³ (Sahih Muslim Mawahib-ud-Dunya. Vol.1, p.293)

⁴ <https://www.reviewofreligions.org/2190/hadhrat-%E2%80%98A%E2%80%99ishah-siddiqahra-and-the-holy-prophetsaw-%E2%80%93-a-relationship-of-love/>

Suhayl who came from Makkah as their representative objected to writing of Muhammad the apostle of Allah so only “to which Muhammad consented” was written. Ali may Allah be pleased with him wrote this document.

Through Hudaibiya he showed the exemplary behaviour to the Muslims and the world, that at the time of conflict when his own intentions were peaceful and the other party was ready to hold a peaceful dialogue, he chose peace over conflict and made a pact.⁵

He was a teacher, he established schools and learning centers for organized education. In Makkah a house was established for the Muslims to learn the religion from the Prophet pbuh named Dar ul Arqam and in Madinah too the Prophet established the masjid, masjid e nabwi as a learning center along with a place of prayer for the Muslims to learn the religion of Islam. Al Arqam’s house was located at the east of Safa Hill and was selected for meetings, prayers and learning in the early days of Prophetic mission in Makkah. It was in a narrow street and could be surveillance from inside. It came to be known as the House of Islam. Muhammad was the teacher and the Muslims were the first students, it could be regarded as the first Islamic school.

Who ever converted was brought to Al Arqam’s house, Hamza and Umar the two powerful citizens converted to Islam in the sixth year and came to this house to proclaim it.

Al-Arqam bequeathed his house to his son on the condition that it would not be sold. However, in the time of Abu Jaafar al-Mansur, one of Al-Arqam’s grandsons was persuaded to sell his share in the house for 17,000 dinars in exchange for being released from prison; and his relatives were then bribed into selling their own shares. His house is now called Daru’l-Khayzuran after a subsequent owner. It is opposite the Kaaba and is used as a religious school today.⁶

In the first year of hijrah after his arrival into Madinah masjid Al Nabwi was built by the Prophet, he bought the land from Sahal and Suhayl instead of accepting it as a gift. The land at one end had been previously used as a burial ground.

He was a father-in-law who would advice his son in laws, would visit them and give them meaning full nick names.

Once Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him said to his people “if I am the city of knowledge, then Ali is the gateway of that city”.

He honoured his son in laws, all three of them, Uthman, Ali and Abu Al As. Uthman was shy, Ali was known for his bravery, while Abu Al As was a just man.

He was a preacher, a caller to Islam, he used systematic ways to call people to Islam. During the pact of hudaibiyah he wrote letters to the neighbouring tribes and invited them to Islam and put a seal on it. That seal was made by his ring which had engraved on it Muhammad Rasool Allah, because of this preaching, many tribes accepted Islam.

In a letter sent to Egyptian ruler Al-Muqawqis in the sixth year of hijri, the prophet invited him to Islam and said if he becomes a Muslim, Allah will double his reward. The prophet also cited the surah: Say, ‘O People of the Scripture, come to a word that is equitable between us and you - that we will not worship except Allah and not associate anything with Him and not take one another as lords instead of Allah.’ But if they turn away, then say: ‘Bear witness that we are Muslims [submitting to Him].’ The prophet also sent letters to Emperor Ashama ibn Abjar in Ethiopia, Heraclius, the emperor of the Byzantine Empire, Chosroes, the king of Persia, Munzir ibn Sawa, the ruler of Bahrain, Himyarite Harith, the prince of Yemen, and Harith Gassani, the governor of Sham. The prophet’s letters inviting kings and princes to follow Islam were all concluded with the statement: If turn away, you will bear the sin of your followers. According to some historic narratives, Chosroes of Persia tore the prophet’s letter. When the Prophet heard that, he promised the destruction of Chosroes and the latter died shortly after and the empire weakened. Some of these letters are kept in the Istanbul Museum while the Medina Museum in Saudi Arabia keeps the original copies of these letters.

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Treaty_of_Hudaybiyyah

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Al-Arqam_ibn_Abi_al-Arqam#:~:text=The%20House%20of%20Al%20Arqam&text=In%20the%20fifth%20of,first%20Muslims%20as%20its%20students.

He was a friend, he confided in his friend on special occasions. Abu Bakr was his friend from before he gained prophethood, when the permission of migration came, he told Abu Bakr about it and the two of them planned this journey together.

Prophet Muhammad (Salutations upon him) showed his great love and respect for Abu Bakr by associating him with the concept of closest friend. In Arabic, the word used is Khaleel and it denotes more than friendship, rather heartfelt closeness with an unbreakable connection. "if I had taken anyone as my closest friend I would have taken Abu Bakr, but he is my brother and companion." These are the words of the Prophet Muhammad (may God shower him with mercy). Abu Bakr was known as Siddeeq (the truthful). The Arabic word Siddique implies more than lack of deceit; it indicates a person in a constant state of truthfulness.

Showed how he chose a Siddique to associate the concept of closeness as a friend.⁷

He was a neighbour, a neighbour who was gentle enough not to disturb his neighbours with loud noise. He had a neighbour, an old lady who would throw garbage on him when he passed by her place after his announcement of prophethood but when she fell ill and stopped this action for a few days, he got concerned about her and visited her.

The Prophet of Allah Muhammad bin Abdullah told the Muslims not to refuse small kindnesses to the neighbours if you are not at war with them, not to cut relation with them and not to shun them.

Ibn Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) said that he heard the Prophet (Salutations upon him) say,

How many neighbours will be attached to a person on the Resurrection Day and will ask Allah, 'Oh Lord, ask him why he closed his door on me, denying me any help he could have given?!

[related by Al-Bukhari in Al-Adab Al-Mufrad collection of hadith].

Just as a person loves good for himself, he should love good for his neighbour according to the sayings of the Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him,

Anas (Salutations upon him) reported that the Prophet (Salutations upon him) said,

By Whom my soul is in His Hands, a person does not» [truly]« believe until he loves for his neighbour --or brother-- what he loves for himself.

The prophet advised us to give food to our neighbours, «If you cook stock, increase the amount of water in it; remember your neighbours and give them from it. »

The Prophet (Salutations upon him) warned his followers from hurting neighbours. In fact, he said a person who hurts his neighbour has no faith. The Prophet (Salutations upon him) even took an oath by Allah to stress this point. The Prophet (Salutations upon him) said,

'By Allah, he does not believe; by Allah, he does not believe; by Allah, he does not believe.' He was asked, "Who, Oh Prophet?" The Prophet (Salutations upon him) replied, 'One whose neighbour is not safe from his harm'» [related by Al-Bukhari].

In fact, good deeds will not benefit their owner, even if they are many, if he used to hurt his neighbour. Abu Hurayrah (may Allah be pleased with him) explained this fact, saying,

A man told the Prophet that so-and-so was known for his great number of prayers, fasts and charity, but he used to hurt his neighbours with his [sharp] tongue. The Prophet (peace be upon him) said, 'He is in the hellfire.' Then the man said that so-and-so was known to fast and pray only a little and give only a little amount of charity, but he was truthful and did not hurt his neighbours with his [sharp] tongue. The Prophet (Salutations upon him) said, 'He is in paradise' [related by Ahmed].

Abu Hurayrah (may Allah be pleased with him) also reported that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said,

⁷ <https://www.arabnews.com/news/510406#:~:text=%E2%80%9CIf%20I%20had,adheres%20to%20it.>

Oh Muslim women, do not consider any gift too small for your neighbour, even if it was bones and hooves of the sheep [related by Al-Bukhari].

The Prophet (Salutations upon him) said that being good to neighbours is a sign of faith, and that hurting neighbours is a sign of lack of faith.

If there is any personality that has lived on the face of this earth who was complete in every regard and the life of whom can serve as a beacon of guidance for people of every walk of life, that personality would undeniably be the personality of Muhammad (Salutations upon him).

The key factor that brings reverence and respect to Prophet Muhammad (Salutations upon him) in both the Islamic and the non-Islamic circles is His character. He was the best in character, and He also said about that in one of His hadiths in the following way:

“God has sent me to perfect good manners and to do good deeds.” (Bukhari)

The lines below discuss some major character traits of Prophet (Salutations upon him) that every Muslim should spread as much as possible.

Even though he was a Prophet, he still posses a sense of Humor, he had the finest sense of humor, such that no one possessed, but it was not vulgar humor, did not debase or make fun of anyone,

Anas (May Allah be pleased with him) reports such an example by saying: “Once a man asked Muhammad (Salutations be upon him) for an animal to ride. He replied that He would give him the baby of a she-camel to ride on. The man asked, ‘What would he do with a she-camel baby?’ Muhammad (Salutation be upon him) replied, ‘Is there any camel which is not born of a she-camel?’” Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be Upon him was a generous person, he fulfilled the needs of others, “The Prophet (PBUH) did not refuse to give anything which He had to someone if he asked for it.” (Bukhari)

His acts of generosity should be spread and aspired to. The most rights in this world have been given to women by Islam, rights and special respect was given to women by Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him. “Whoever (brings up) two girls till they come of age, will be in the next world along with me, like my two fingers joining each other.” (Abu Dawud)

Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him had a pleasant personality, with smile and gentleness he greeted the people,

“I have never seen a man who smiled as much as the Messenger of Allah.” (Tirmidhi)

Prophet Muhammad took special care of the Orphans and asked his companions to do the same, he said,

“The best house among the Muslims is one where an orphan is well treated, and the worst house among the Muslims is one where an orphan is badly treated.”⁸

Even though Prophet Muhammad was at the top of the leading position at that time, when it came to difficult time he helped his companions and worked with them, at the battle of trench what happened was narrated by one of his companions,

“I saw the Messenger of Allah on the Day of the Trench carrying dirt (that was dug from the trench) until His chest was covered with dirt.” (Bukhari)

Not just people but he also took care of animals, instead of mistreating the animals, he told them to be nice and kind to them and be fair with them, Aisha r.a narrated,

“I once found difficulty in riding a horse, so I kept reining it in repeatedly. The Prophet (PBUH) then said, ‘You must have gentleness.’”⁹

⁸ (Ibn Majah)

⁹(Muslim)

The Prophet of Allah Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him had no interest in worldly possession, what he left behind was knowledge and not worldly possessions,

“The Messenger of Allah did not leave any gold or silver currency, or a slave, male or female, after his death. He only left behind his white mule, his weapons, and a piece of land which He declared as charity.”¹⁰

He was modest. Bashful and encouraged these two qualities in his life,

“Modesty is a part of teachings of the previous Prophets and anyone who lacks it is most likely to do whatever he likes.”¹¹

Thus, modesty is imperative to Islam and Prophet (salutations be upon him) being a living and breathing Islam ascertains that He was modest in every respect. He was considerate and kind to everyone, he said “I stand up for prayer intending to prolong it. In the meantime, I hear the wailing of a baby and I must shorten my prayer, being apprehensive lest my recitation of a long verse may tell upon the baby’s mother.” (Bukhari)¹²

Surely Allah conferred a great favor on the believers when He raised from among them a Messenger to recite to them His signs, and to purify them, and to teach them the Book and Wisdom. For before that they were in manifest error.¹³

Indisputably, the Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him) was the greatest teacher that the world had and will ever witness. Through him, the laws of Islam were sealed, and the last holy book was revealed. With utter integrity and honesty, our beloved prophet (salutations be upon him) completed his assigned duty of a tutor to mankind. He exhibited the ways of true leadership and gave another lesson humanity desperately needed. He was sent to one of the most ignorant human race of the time. Yet, Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him) was able to teach them, not with mere words but wise actions as well. His ways were an epitome of the quote ‘actions speak louder than words’.

Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be Upon him was especially merciful to the children. Abu Huraira reported that al-Aqra’ b. Habis saw Allah’s Apostle (ﷺ) kissing Hasan. Al Aqra said: I have ten children, but I have never kissed anyone of them, whereupon Allah’s Messenger (ﷺ) said: “Whoever is not merciful to others will not be treated mercifully.” Reported by Bukhari (Book 78, Hadith 6063) The Bedouins were not used to showing affection to the children, they considered it against the norms of the society. Prophet was always kind to children and never questioned their choices, in fact always praised and appreciated them, The Prophet’s servant Anas said: “I served the Prophet for ten years and he never once rebuked me. He never once said about something I did: ‘Why did you do that?’ and he never said about something I didn’t do: ‘Why didn’t you do that?’¹⁴

One such example can be seen from His life when He used to say to kids:

“I’ll give such and such (i.e., gift or so) to the one who comes to me first.”

So, they used to race and fall on His back and chest. (Ahmad)

This shows His treatment towards kids and there are countless other examples in His lifetime where He commanded parents to be loving and caring towards their children.

The greatest act of forgiveness was seen on the day of the fath ul Makkah, the conquest of Makkah, when Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him forgave the Quresh even though they had caused him great harm, tortured, ridiculed, abused, him when he was in Makkah during the 13 year after he gained prophet hood, not only this but when he immigrated to Madinah they kept battling him and his honour, refused him the Umrah. Even when his dear ones were attacked, he didn’t take revenge from such people although he had the control to do so. As a teacher which the

¹⁰ (Bukhari)

¹¹ (Reported by Abdullah ibn Maslamah)

¹² <http://www.quranreading.com/blog/things-about-the-character-of-prophet-muhammad-pbuh-every-muslim-must-spread/>

¹³ (Al Quran - Al-Imraan 3:164)

¹⁴ (Saheeh Al-bukhari; Vol. 8, Book 73, Hadith 64 Sunan Abi Daud Book 42, Hadith 4756)

Prophet of Allah peace and blessings of Allah be upon him was all his life, forgiveness was necessary and most significant, his each action taught a million words and sensations,

“...This day have I perfected your religion for you, completed My Grace upon you, and have chosen Islam for you as your religion...” (Al Maaida 5:3) Through him was the completion of perfection done, Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him) the greatest teacher of all time.¹⁵

Slavery is one of the most cruel and hideous habit of the society. Since the early history of man kind, it has been present. It was considered necessary and right by many nations and even by intellectual scholars that is why it had penetrated the human societies. There were no steps taken to abolish or to amend it in those societies. The slaves and the free men were created as human beings according to the Greek, as a necessity to Human beings, the system of slavery was created according to Aristotle. According to Aristotle attention should be paid to improvement of life but slavery should be used when more manpower is used. However, the prophet peace and blessings of Allah be upon him upon him understood that humans are alike in terms of their nature and posses the same kinds of emotions, wills, sentiments, soul etc. With the social growth the social situation had to be improved. With thought and wisdom, he put this into effect.

He said: Whites have no natural privilege over Blacks, and the worst of people in the sight of God are slave traders. Slaves are your brothers. They have been put under your command and they have their own rights. You should feed them of what you eat and dress them of what you wear. Do not ask them to do things beyond their capacity and help them to do things. When you call them, call them politely and do not say, ‘My slave’ or ‘my slave-girl’. Rather, you should say, ‘my lad’, ‘my lass’ or ‘my boy’. All your men and all your women are servants of God, and He is the True Master of all.

Slavery in its primitive form was established in the mind of many people and now the heart touching messages from the Prophet, the greatest humanitarian of the time was changing the prospects, the inferiority that the slaves had been buried under and the arrogance the masters had was melting, and everyone was realizing that its time to treat the slaves on the basis of equality.

This way through the encouragement and positive enforcement of the Prophet (salutations be upon him) freeing of the slaves was made possible and people were encouraged to do so, they were encouraged by way of telling them and promising them that their sins would be expiated and their repentance would be accepted or the slaves would be emancipated, they could buy their own freedom or through bait ul maal, the public treasury.

This way slavery died out gradually because Prophet gave so many ways that it could be blocked. By practical example he freed his own slave Zayd ibn Haritha who was gifted to him by his wife. Khadijah. So, who ever wants to follow the sunnah should do the same. The adopted son, Zayd was called and married later to the cousin of Prophet (salutations be upon him). In this way racial superiority was also abolished.¹⁶

Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him) was merciful as well as brave. He used to fast and pray all night. He was the commander for the Muslims during times of battle and along side Muslims fought the enemies, such enemies who had come to destroy and attack the Muslims. During such battles, Al-Bara (May Allah be pleased with him) reported: By Allah, when the fighting became fierce, we would seek protection by his side and the bravest among us was the one who confronted the onslaught. It was the Prophet (salutations be upon him).¹⁷

Anas may Allah be pleased with him, one of the Prophet’s (salutations be upon him) companions, said that there was no person whom they loved more than the Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him yet when he came to them, they did not stand up for him because he hated their standing up for him, as other people do with their great people.¹⁸

¹⁵ <https://edubirdie.com/examples/personal-and-teaching-traits-of-prophet-muhammad/>

¹⁶ <https://www.al-islam.org/message-thaqalayn/vol11-n4-2011/glimpse-character-traits-prophet-muhammad-part-1/glimpse-character>

¹⁷ [Muslim 1776: Grade Sahih]

¹⁸ Narrated in Mosnad Ahmad, #12117, and Al-Tirmizi, #2754

Anas May Allah be pleased with him, one of the Prophet's (salutations be upon him) companions, said that there was no person whom they loved more than the Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him), yet when he came to them, they did not stand up for him because he hated their standing up for him, as other people do with their great people.¹⁹

The Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him chose to live by his own earnings even when he was the leader of the nation and full control and access to the treasury. Aa'isha (May Allah be pleased with him), Prophet Muhammad's (salutations be upon him) wife, said, "O my nephew, we would sight three new moons in two months without lighting a fire (to cook a meal) in the Prophet's houses." Her nephew asked, "O Aunt, what sustained you?" She said, "The two black things, dates and water, but the Prophet had some Ansar neighbors who had milk-giving she-camels and they used to send the Prophet some of its milk." (Saheeh Muslim, #2972, and Saheeh Al-Bukhari, #2567) Sahl Ibn Sa'ad (May Allah be pleased with him), one of Prophet Muhammad's (salutations be upon him) companions, said, "The Prophet of God did not see bread made from fine flour from the time God sent him (as a prophet) until he died."²⁰

An envoy of the pagan leaders, Otba, came to Prophet Muhammad (salutations be upon him) saying, "...If you want money, we will collect enough money for you so that you will be the richest one of us. If you want leadership, we will take you as our leader and never decide on any matter without your approval. If you want a kingdom, we will crown you king over us..." Only one concession was required from Muhammad (salutations be upon him) in return for that, to give up calling people to Islam and worshiping God alone without any partner. The Prophet (salutations be upon him) replied with the following answer: 'In the Name of God, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful, ...' And he recited to Otba the Ayahs of the Quran 41:1-38. (Al-Serah Al-Nabaweyyah, Ibn Hesham, vol. 1, pp. 293-294.) The Following are some of these Ayahs:

A revelation from (God), the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful; a Book whereof the Ayahs are explained in detail; a Quran in Arabic, for people who know, giving good news and warning, yet most of them turn away, so they do not listen.²¹

On another occasion, in response to his uncle's plea to stop calling people to Islam, Muhammad's (salutations be upon him) answer was as decisive and sincere: "I swear by the name of God, O Uncle!, that if they place the sun in my right-hand and the moon in my left-hand in return for giving up this matter (calling people to Islam), I will never desist until either God makes it triumph or I perish defending it."²²(Al-Serah Al-Nabaweyyah, Ibn Hesham, vol. 1, pp. 265-266.)

Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him possessed the best character and he was sent to spread the best character as well. Abu Huraira (may Allah be pleased with him) reported: The Messenger of Allah, (salutations be upon him), said: Verily, I have only been sent to perfect righteous character.²³

Malice, envy and arrogance are not present in good character. A person with good character holds righteousness dearer than worldly things and has integrity. Abdullah ibn Amr (May Allah be pleased with him) reported: It was said to the Messenger of Allah, "Which of the people is best?" The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, said: Everyone who is pure of heart and truthful in speech. They said, "Truthful in speech we know, but what is a pure heart?" The Prophet said: It is a heart that fears Allah and is clean. There is no sin in it and neither aggression, malice, nor envy.²⁴ An-Nawwas ibn Sam'an May Allah be upon him reported: The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, said: Righteousness is good character and sin is what waivers in your heart and you hate for people to find out about it.²⁵ And the Prophet peace and blessings of Allah be upon him said: Consult your soul, consult your heart. Righteousness is what reassures your soul and your heart, and sin is what wavers in your soul and puts tension in your

¹⁹ Narrated in Mosnad Ahmad, #12117, and Al-Tirmizi, #2754

²⁰ (Saheeh Al-Bukhari, #5413, and Al-Tirmizi, #2364)

²¹ (Quran, Surah Fussilat 41: Ayahs 2-4)

²²

²³ [Musnad Ahmad 8729, Grade: Sahih]

²⁴ [Sunan Ibn Mājah 4216, Grade: Sahih]

²⁵ [Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim 2553, Grade: Sahih].

chest, even if the people approve it in their judgments again and again.²⁶ And, in another narration, narrated from al-Hasan ibn ‘Ali May Allah be pleased with him, the grandson of the Prophet peace and blessings of Allah upon him who said: I memorized from the Messenger of Allah (salutations be upon him): “Leave that which makes you doubt for that which does not make you doubt, for truth leads to reassurance and lies leads to uncertainty.”²⁷

If a Muslim’s character is good then he is a good person, goodness in character means goodness in behaviour and personality and manners. Abdullah ibn Amr (May Allah be pleased with him) reported: The Messenger of Allah, peace and blessings of Allah be upon him, said: The best of you is those with the best character.²⁸ Abu Huraira (May Allah be pleased with him) reported: The Messenger of Allah, (salutations be upon him) said: The most complete of the believers in faith are those with the most excellent character, and the best of you are the best in behavior to their women. [Sunan al-Tirmidhī 1162, Grade: Sahih] Jabir ibn Samurah (May Allah be pleased with him) reported: The Messenger of Allah, (salutations be upon him), said: Verily, obscenity and immorality are not part of Islam. Verily, the best people in Islam are those with the best character.²⁹³⁰

Prophet Muhammad was called Al Amin and is still remembered so because he was loved and exemplary since childhood, he possessed noble characters. He also participated with his people in renewing the building of the Kaaba. He helped his uncle Abbas to move the stones. When his people wanted to put the Black Stone in its place, they argued over who deserved the glory, and the dispute almost ended in a battle.

Abu Umayyah bin Mughirah al-Mahzumi, a sage, was unmoved to see this situation. With all his wisdom, he exclaimed “O my people, enough of this dispute. Let’s appoint an intermediary. Let the one who put this stone be the first person to enter the mosque today.” They accepted this suggestion. A few moments later, Prophet Muhammad peace and blessings of Allah be upon him appeared calmly and stepped into the Masjid al-Haram. Seeing that the people welcomed him with joy. They felt that Prophet Muhammad ﷺ was very deserving of this noble work. Honesty, politeness and nobility of morality make them ashamed to disapprove of it.

They said, “He is al-Amin, we are happy with his decision”.

3. CONCLUSION

Prophet Muhammad was a leader, and his leadership theory was incorporated in daily action too. Concept of personal awareness as a leader was one of the leadership concepts that he proclaimed. Many people in the world are still not aware that he was a leader with roles and responsibilities. By way of deliberation and consensus he decided all matters. This he did because he obeyed Allah’s command as stated in Surah Ali ‘Imran:

“It is part of the Mercy of Allah that thou dost deal gently with them. Wert thou severe or harsh-hearted, they would have broken away from about thee: so, pass over (Their faults), and ask for (Allah’s) forgiveness for them; and consult them in affairs (of moment). Then, when thou hast Taken a decision put thy trust in Allah. For Allah loves those who put their trust (in Him).”³¹

He called his subordinates as companions and not as subordinate.

Prophet Muhammad (salutation be upon him) treated everyone equally, he never discriminated against anyone.

The Prophet (salutations be upon him) was even very close to his companions like Bilal who was a slave but freed later by Abu Bakr and he was also close to Anas bin Malik.

²⁶ [Sunan al-Dārimī 2533, Grade: Hasan]

²⁷ [Tirmidhi (2442), Ahmad (1630) and Ibn Hibbaan (722) Graded: saheeh by al-Albaani].

²⁸ [Ṣaḥīḥ al-Bukhārī 3366, Grade: Muttafaquun Alayhi]

²⁹ [Musnad Aḥmad 20320, Grade: Sahih]

³⁰ <https://portalislam.org/index.php/his-character>

³¹ [Ali ‘Imran 3:159]

The Prophet (salutations be upon him) was appreciative of Muslims and non-Muslims alike. On the outskirts of the market, he would feed the blind poor Jews as well. Allah has created us differently but the only difference in his eyes is that of piety.

“O mankind, we have created you from a male and a female, and made you into races and tribes, so that you may identify one another. Surely the noblest of you, in Allah’s sight, is the one who is most pious of you. Surely Allah is All-Knowing, All-Aware”.^{32 33}

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